

EFFECTIVENESS OF BLENDED LEARNING IN THE INSTRUCTION OF ENGLISH GRAMMAR AT PRIMARY LEVEL

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Abstract

This study educates the effectiveness of Blended Learning in the instruction of English grammar among the primary students. Traditional methods challenged to enhance the English grammar among the students. Investigators of the study endeavoured to practice Blended Learning for enrich the knowledge and understanding English grammar. Experimental method was adopted in the study. Seventy students at standard V, Bhavans Vidyashram, Malappuram were selected as sample for the study. Thirty five students were considered as Controlled group and another Thirty five were considered as Experimental group. Researcher's self-made achievement test was used as a tool for the study. Blended Learning is more effective than traditional methods in the instruction of English grammar.

Key Words: Effectiveness, Blended Learning, Experimentation, and Traditional Methods.

Introduction

Blended Learning technique is applied by the student where learning happens both as online and offline mode. It will be done either as self-learning or contact classes keeping in mind the effective collaboration of learning. The contact classes enhance the skill development, critical mindset and positive and active behaviour which are very much needed for interactive classroom. The self-learning mode can be little apprehensive and may not cater to the interest of the learner all the time. The blended learning is an innovative design that developed to enhance the learning skills especially in grammar where it will enrich the student to think and evaluate themselves about their knowledge in a particular area. It helps the student to develop experiences which will be utilised by them throughout their life.

Bataineh, Khaleel Bader; Banikalef, Ala'Eddin Abdullah Ahmed; Albashtawi, Abeer H (2019). The blended learning approach and its application to teach English was the hot topic of discussion nowadays. The mixed method of study aimed at examining the effects of the blended learning approach and attitudes of Jordanian EFL learner's grammar performance. They used quasi experimental design and qualitative interviews for their studies. The quasi-experimental design study involves two groups – experimental and control groups. 70 students were taken as sample for the study. 35 students were there in experimental group and 35 students were taken as sample for control group. The experimental group were taught using Moodle and control group were taught using conventional methods. All the students in experimental group were interviewed after the teaching. The students in experimental group have done well

compare to control group. The qualitative analysis result showed that blended learning is far way better than conventional methods. The blended learning motivated the learner to learn English further without any hesitation. So, it is concluded that blended learning is more effective to teach English grammar.

Hashemi, Aminuddin; Si Na, Kew (2020) Languages always cater to the four skills such as reading, writing, speaking and listening. The blended learning always caters and enhances the four skills positively. The blended learning encourages students to develop the attitude towards learning and promote the self-learning. The blended learning is considered as 21st century skills which have to be considered for teaching in the future.

Objectives

1. To identify the obstacles faced by the students in learning English grammar in the classroom atmosphere.
2. To find out the significant difference in achievement mean score between the pre-test of control group and the post-test of control group.
3. To find out the significant difference in achievement mean score between the pre-test of Experimental group and the post-test of Experimental group.
4. To find out the impact of Blended Learning in the instruction of English grammar in classroom atmosphere.

Hypotheses

1. Students have problems in learning English grammar in school atmosphere.
2. There is no significant difference in achievement mean score between the pre-test of control group and the post-test of control group.
3. There is no significant difference in achievement mean score between the pre-test of Experimental group and the post-test of Experimental group.
4. Blended Learning is more effective than traditional methods in the instruction of English grammar.

Variables

The independent variable is indicated as Blended Learning

The dependent variable is taken as achievement test score were used in this study.

Methodology

Sample

Equivalent group Experimental method was adopted in the study.

70 Students of standard V from Bhavans Vidyashram, Malappuram, Kerala were selected as sample for the study. Thirty-five students were considered as Controlled group and another thirty-five were considered as Experimental group.

Tool

Researcher's self-made achievement test was used as a tool for the study. Pre-test and post-test were conducted for this study. Validity of the tool was established by the opinion of the senior teachers. Reliability of the tool was established by the split-half method.

Preparation of tool

The investigator's self-made Achievement test was used for the pre-tests and post-tests of both control groups and experimental groups. The same questions were used for both pre and post-tests to evaluate scoring in learning English grammar through objective types of question which carried one mark for each question and contained 50 marks. First researcher conducted pre-test after that test evaluation some treatment given to the experimental group. After that treatment again conducted the achievement test used with the same questions.

Establishment of Reliability

Reliability of the tool had been computed using split-half method and the calculated value is 0.81. The value is quite significant and implies that the tools adopted were reliable. Hence the reliability was established for the study.

Validity of the tool

Subject experts, experienced and senior teachers were requested to analyse the tool. Their opinions indicated that the tool had content validity.

Procedure of the study

1. Identification of the problem in conventional and traditional method by administering pre-test to the both groups
2. Preparation of activities for Blended teaching Learning process.
3. Treatment.
4. Administering the post-test.

Procuring Data

The researcher administered pre-test to the students with the help of a teachers and Principal. The question papers were given to the students and evaluated the instruction and learning obstacles of the students through the pre-test. The causes of low achievement by uncomfortable methods were found out. Blended Learning was used in the classroom for improving and enrich English grammar for two weeks. The post-test was administered and the effectiveness of the Blended Learning was found out.

Statistical Techniques Used

Mean, Standard Deviation and t-test were computed for the study.

Results**Hypothesis - 1**

Students have problems in learning English grammar by traditional methods or conventional method. In the post-test, students scored 76% of marks and the students scored 24% of marks in the conventional method.

Hypothesis - 2

There is no significant difference between the Pre-Test Control Group and Post Test Control Group in achievement mean scores of the students in learning English grammar at standard V.

Test	N	Mean	S.D	t value	Result
Pre Test control Group	35	22.56	3.56	1.028	Not significant at 0.05 level
Post Test control Group	35	22.67	2.24		

The calculated "t" value is (1.028) less than table value (2.04). Hence null hypothesis is accepted at 0.05 levels. Hence there is no significant difference between the Pre-Test of Control Group and Post Test of Control Group in achievement mean scores of the students in learning English grammar at standard V.

Hypothesis - 3

There is no significant difference in achievement mean score between the Pre-Test Experimental Group and Post Test Experimental Group.

Test	N	Mean	S.D	t value	Result
Pre Test Experimental Group	35	22.31	2.95	12.26	Significant at 0.05 level
Post Test Experimental Group	35	36.85	5.89		

The calculated 't' value is (12.26) greater than table value (2.04). Hence null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level. Hence there is significant difference between the Pre-Test Experimental Group and Post Test

Experimental Group in achievement mean scores of the students by learning English grammar through Blended learning in classroom atmosphere.

Hypothesis - 4

Blended Learning is more effective than existing methods in learning English grammar.

Achievement mean scores of the learners in Post Test of Control Group is 22.67 and the achievement mean scores of the learners Post Test of Experimental Group is 36.85. Score of the Post Test of Experimental Group (36.85) is greater than Pre-Test of Experimental Group (22.31). Above both assure that learning English grammar by using Blended Learning is more effective than conventional methods

Findings

1. In the post-test, Students of standard V scored 76% of marks and the students scored 24% of marks in the conventional method or traditional method in classroom atmosphere.
2. There is no significant difference between the Pre- test of control group and Post-test of control group in achievement mean scores of the students in learning English grammar.
3. There is a significant difference in achievement mean score between the Pre-test of

Experimental group and Post-test of Experimental group

4. Blended Learning is more effective than traditional methods in the instruction of English grammar in classroom atmosphere.

Educational Implications

1. Blended Learning can be extended to primary level, secondary level and higher secondary level and higher education level.

2. It can be encouraged to implement the use in school education and college education system

3. It may be activated in school education and higher education level.

5. Proper orientation is needed for Teachers in Blended learning.

6. Implement infrastructure facilities and training programme for teachers.

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